

[original idea/conjecture]

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Molecular construction in the relational quantum vacuum

Open Quantum Collaboration*†

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Abstract

We conjecture that the quantum vacuum fluctuations operate through abstract mathematical relations of relations. Then we show how to construct a number of molecules from simple rules. Although this is an application of the Wolfram model, the conjecture itself is more general and therefore does not restrict to its rules.

keywords: conjecture, molecules, quantum vacuum, Wolfram model

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/n5rzy/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/6792743>

Introduction

1. This white paper is an *application* of the **Wolfram model** [1–4].
2. Mathematical relations are the generalization of functions [5].
3. Functions have been successfully applied to describe nature.

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4. So it is pretty natural to think that rules operating in the quantum fabric of spacetime might not be constrained by the mathematical restrictions that functions impose.
5. It is also natural to suppose that nature has a recursive *modus operandi*, meaning that one fixed rule applies iteratively over and over again to one specific system.

The model

6. **Conjecture.**
Quantum vacuum fluctuations are governed by the relation
 $r : R_1 \rightarrow R_2$.
7. Particularly, here we associate (6) with the rules designed in the Wolfram model [1].
8. `node` := atom
9. `edge` := chemical bond
10. `event` := each iteration of r
11. We consider that one molecule is created if the transformations on the relations converge to a fixed graph after a finite number of events.

Notation

12. (a, b) := ordered pair
13. r, R_1, R_2 := binary relations
14. We use the signature $2_2 \rightarrow 4_2$ of the Wolfram model,

$$r : \{(x_1, x_2), (x_3, x_4)\} \rightarrow \{(y_1, y_2), (y_3, y_4), (y_5, y_6), (y_7, y_8)\}.$$

15. $x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 \in X = \{1, 2, 3\}$
16. $y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_7, y_8 \in Y = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$
17. The choice of the sets X and Y was arbitrary; we assumed few numbers in each of them so that more interactions between nodes could occur.

Molecules

18. (14) generated the following molecules [6].
19. 1,2,4,5-Tetraoxaspiro[2.2]pentane: C_0O_4
20. 1-Oxa-2,3-diaza-2-cyclopropene: N_2O
21. 1H-diazirine: CH_2N_2
22. Carbon dioxide: CO_2
23. CID 20713240: O_2^{--}
24. CID 22955401: HO_3^-
25. Diazenide: HN_2^+
26. Formylaminoradical: CH_2NO^-
27. Hydrogen cyanide: CHN
28. Methylium: CH_3^+
29. Nitrite: NO_2^-
30. Nitroxyl: HNO
31. Oxaziridine-3-one: CHNO_2
32. Oxoazanide: NO^-

33. Oxomethanide: CHO^-

34. Perdeuterodiazirine: CH_2N_2

Oxaziridine-3-one: CHNO_2

35. In order to get acquainted with the basics of Wolfram model, one can follow the pp. 7-12 of [1].

36. The rule for the creation of CHNO_2 , for instance, is given by

$$r : \{(1, 3), (3, 3)\} \rightarrow \{(1, 3), (2, 1), (1, 4), (4, 3)\}.$$

37. It becomes more clear when we replace the numbers in r with variables.

38. Assigning $1 \rightsquigarrow x$, $3 \rightsquigarrow y$, $2 \rightsquigarrow z$, $4 \rightsquigarrow w$, we have

$$r : \{(x, y), (y, y)\} \rightarrow \{(x, y), (z, x), (x, w), (w, y)\}.$$

39. The first set of r is being mapped to the second set iteratively.

40. Then the graph for this rule is

41. The initial condition starts with two binary self-loops, $(1, 1), (1, 1)$,

42. The evolution of CHNO_2 is then accomplished in two events, namely,

43. The first iteration is thus given by

$$r : \{(1, 1), (1, 1)\} \rightarrow \{(1, 1), (2, 1), (1, 3), (3, 1)\},$$

which results in

44. From the second iteration and after, the updating and convergence processes are more complicated and are explained in [7].

45. The **individual updating events** are comprised by

46. One can check [7] for more detailed information about the meaning of the individual updating events depicted in the diagram.

47. The **multiway system**, in which is included a separate path for every possible updating event that can occur is

48. Similarly, one can check [7] for more detailed information about the meaning of the multiway system depicted in the diagram.

More Results

49. Check the Appendix.

Final Remarks

50. The underlying idea of our work is that the quantum nature of space-time operates by means of zillions of mathematical relations such that the right physical conditions (material and energetic resources, for example) results in the production of particles, fields, and even in the very creation of the laws of physics in the light of Leibniz principle of no unreciprocated actions [8].
51. Of course there are plenty of further work that needs to be done in order to extract the precise mathematical instructions that operate in the quantum vacuum so that one day we can fully unveil the ultimate secrets of the universe.

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [9, 10].

*Join the **Open Quantum Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to `mplobo@uft.edu.br`.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [11, 12].

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Agreement

The author agrees with [10].

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Appendix

We present two collection of experiments in the following notebooks: `b1.nb` and `b2.nb`. Not every object in the list is in direct correspondence to a molecule. This is an open science project, anyone can contribute to this white paper, please contact mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Signature 2_2->4_2 (experiment 1)

All initial conditions start at $\{(1,1),(1,1)\}$.

Oxaziridine-3-one: CHNO2

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/17769893>

$r: \{(1,3), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(1,3), (2,1), (1,4), (4,3)\}$

Oxirene: C2H2O

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/160438>

$r: \{(3,2), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,3), (4,2), (3,4), (2,1)\}$

1,2,4,5-Tetraoxaspiro[2.2]pentane: CO4

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/5256172>

$r: \{(1,1), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(1,2), (3,1), (1,4), (4,2)\}$

1H-diazirine: CH₂N₂Perdeuterodiazirine: CH₂N₂

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/15929988>

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/129693596>

$r: \{(2,3), (3,2)\} \rightarrow \{(1,3), (2,1), (4,1), (1,3)\}$

Methylium: CH₃⁺

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/644094>

$r: \{(1,1), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(4,1), (3,4), (4,2), (4,4)\}$

Oxomethanide: CHO-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/12485890>

$r: \{(2,1), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,3), (3,1), (3,4), (3,2)\}$

Diazenide: HN₂⁺

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/5460526>

$r: \{(2,1), (1,2)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (4,2), (3,4), (4,2)\}$

Carbon dioxide: CO₂

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/280>

$r: \{(2,2), (2,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (3,2), (1,4), (1,4)\}$

O5--

$r: \{(3,1), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (1,4), (4,3), (2,2)\}$

NO2-

$r: \{(2,3), (2,3)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (4,1), (4,3), (3,2)\}$

CID 20713240: O3--

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/20713240>

$r: \{(3,3), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,4), (2,2), (3,1), (3,4)\}$

Oxoazanide: NO-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/3001380>

$r: \{(3,3), (2,3)\} \rightarrow \{(1,1), (3,2), (2,4), (2,4)\}$

H2NO?5

$r: \{(1,3), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(4,1), (2,1), (3,1), (3,2)\}$

Oxoazanide: NO⁻

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/3001380>

$r: \{(3,3), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,2), (2,3), (2,3), (4,4)\}$

Oxomethanide: CHO-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/12485890>

$r: \{(1,3), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(1,2), (1,4), (1,3), (2,3)\}$

1-Oxa-2,3-diaza-2-cyclopropene: N2O

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/15764366>

$r: \{(3,3), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(3,2), (4,2), (2,1), (4,1)\}$

$r: \{(1,3), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,2), (1,3), (3,1), (3,2)\}$

$r: \{(2,1), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(4,3), (3,1), (3,4), (1,4)\}$

Nitrite: NO₂-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/946>

$r: \{(3,1), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(4,2), (2,2), (3,4), (4,1)\}$

$r: \{(3,2), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,4), (3,2), (3,2), (1,4)\}$

1H-diazirine: CH₂N₂

Perdeuterodiazirine: CH₂N₂

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/15929988>

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/129693596>

$r: \{ (2,1), (1,1) \} \rightarrow \{ (3,4), (3,1), (2,3), (1,2) \}$

1-Oxa-2,3-diaza-2-cyclopropene: N2O

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/15764366>

$r: \{(2,3), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(3,4), (1,2), (1,4), (1,4)\}$

1-Oxa-2,3-diaza-2-cyclopropene: N2O

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/15764366>

$r: \{(1,1), (2,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (1,4), (1,3), (3,4)\}$

1-Oxa-2,3-diaza-2-cyclopropene: N2O

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/15764366>

$r: \{(2,2), (3,2)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (4,1), (3,4), (3,1)\}$

Oxoazanide: NO-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/3001380>

$r: \{(3,1), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,4), (1,1), (2,2), (2,4)\}$

CID 22955401: HO3-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/22955401>

$r: \{(1,1), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (4,2), (4,4), (3,2)\}$

Formylaminoradical: CH₂NO-

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/12685926>

$r: \{(1,1), (3,1)\} \rightarrow \{(4,2), (1,1), (2,3), (3,2)\}$

Nitroxyl: HNO

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/945>

$r: \{(1,1), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(1,1), (2,3), (4,2), (4,2)\}$

Hydrogen cyanide: CHN

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/768>

$r: \{(1,1), (2,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (1,4), (1,3), (2,3)\}$

Signature 2_2→4_2 (experiment 2)

All initial conditions start at $\{(1,1),(1,1)\}$.

```
xm = 3; ym = 4;
SeedRandom[12];
Do[x1 = RandomInteger[{1, xm}];
  x2 = RandomInteger[{1, xm}];
  x3 = RandomInteger[{1, xm}];
  x4 = RandomInteger[{1, xm}];
  y1 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y2 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y3 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y4 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y5 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y6 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y7 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
  y8 = RandomInteger[{1, ym}];
abc = ResourceFunction["WolframModel"][{{{x1, x2}, {x3, x4}} → {{y1, y2},
  {y3, y4}, {y5, y6}, {y7, y8}}}, {{1, 1}, {1, 1}}, 6, "VertexCountList"];
If[Length[abc] < 7, Print[CellPrint[Cell["", "PageBreak"]];
  Print["(i = ", i, ")"];
  Print["Rule:"];
  Print["r:{"(, x1, ",", x2, ")", (" x3, ",", x4, ")"}->{"(, y1, ",", y2,
  "), (" y3, ",", y4, ")", (" y5, ",", y6, ")", (" y7, ",", y8, ")"}"];
  Print[RulePlot[ResourceFunction["WolframModel"][
    {{{x1, x2}, {x3, x4}} → {{y1, y2}, {y3, y4}, {y5, y6}, {y7, y8}}}],
    VertexLabels → "Name", "RulePartsAspectRatio" → 0.7]];
  Print[""];
  Print["Quantum Dynamics:"];
  ResourceFunction["WolframModelPlot"][#, VertexLabels → Automatic] & /@
    ResourceFunction["WolframModel"][{{{x1, x2}, {x3, x4}} →
    {{y1, y2}, {y3, y4}, {y5, y6}, {y7, y8}}, {{0, 0}, {0, 0}}, 3, "StatesList"]];
  Print[""];
  Print["Individual updating events:"];
  Print[ResourceFunction["WolframModel"][{{{x1, x2}, {x3, x4}} → {{y1, y2}, {y3,
    y4}, {y5, y6}, {y7, y8}}, {{1, 1}, {1, 1}}, 6, "EventsStatesPlotsList"]];
  Print[""];
  Print["Multiway System:"];
  Print[ResourceFunction["MultiwaySystem"]["WolframModel" →
    {{{x1, x2}, {x3, x4}} → {{y1, y2}, {y3, y4}, {y5, y6}, {y7, y8}}},
    {{{1, 1}, {1, 1}}}, 6, "EvolutionEventsGraph", VertexSize → {0.9, 0.3},
    ImageSize → Large] // LayeredGraphPlot]], {i, 1, 100}]
```

(i = 4)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,3), (3,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,2), (2,1), (4,3), (2,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 5)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,1), (3,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,2), (2,4), (3,4), (1,3)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 6)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,3), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(4,1), (1,4), (4,1), (3,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 8)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,1), (2,1)\} \rightarrow \{(4,2), (1,4), (4,3), (1,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 9)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,1), (3,1)\} \rightarrow \{(1,2), (3,1), (2,3), (4,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 15)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,3), (3,2)\} \rightarrow \{(4,1), (4,2), (3,4), (1,3)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 18)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,3), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (3,4), (1,4), (4,3)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 21)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,2), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,4), (4,3), (1,3), (2,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 23)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,1), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (2,4), (2,1), (2,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 24)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,3), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (3,2), (4,1), (3,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 25)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,1), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (1,3), (1,3), (3,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 26)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,3), (3,2)\} \rightarrow \{(2,4), (2,1), (1,1), (4,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 28)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,3), (3,2)\} \rightarrow \{(4,2), (1,2), (2,3), (1,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 29)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,2), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (3,4), (3,4), (2,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 34)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,1), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(2,4), (1,2), (2,3), (1,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 36)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,2), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(4,2), (2,3), (1,3), (4,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 38)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,3), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,2), (4,1), (1,4), (2,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 42)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,1), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(4,3), (3,1), (3,1), (2,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 44)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,3), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (1,3), (2,3), (4,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 45)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,3), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (1,2), (3,4), (3,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 51)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,2), (3,3)\} \rightarrow \{(3,4), (4,2), (1,4), (2,1)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 61)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,1), (1,1)\} \rightarrow \{(2,4), (4,2), (3,1), (2,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 65)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,3), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(1,4), (2,4), (3,2), (1,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 69)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,1), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(3,2), (4,3), (2,1), (1,3)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 71)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,3), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(4,4), (2,4), (2,3), (1,4)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 74)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,1), (2,1)\} \rightarrow \{(3,1), (4,4), (2,3), (3,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 80)

Rule:

r: { (1,1), (1,1) } -> { (4,3), (1,3), (3,2), (1,2) }

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 81)

Rule:

$r: \{(1,1), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(1,4), (4,2), (4,4), (1,3)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 88)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,1), (1,3)\} \rightarrow \{(2,2), (1,2), (1,1), (4,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 89)

Rule:

$r: \{(3,3), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(1,2), (1,3), (4,4), (1,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

(i = 91)

Rule:

$r: \{(2,1), (2,2)\} \rightarrow \{(2,1), (2,1), (2,4), (3,2)\}$

Quantum Dynamics:

Individual updating events:

Multiway System:

